

Double sulfates and related species : contributions of P.C. Rây

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Abstract : Rây worked (1885-1887) for his D.Sc. degree in Edinburgh University on double double sulfates. Double sulfates of type 1 were known for long. In Rây's time there were claims and contradictions that double double sulfates of type 2 also exist. Ray's doctoral work undertaken to sort out this problem led him to conclude that double double sulfates of the flexible composition 3 does exist. Many decades later structural work revealed that all reported double double sulfates can only be solid solutions (mixed crystals) of the constituent isomorphous type 1 salts. At College of Science Rây's group revisited (1927-1930) double sulfate chemistry to achieve cation replacement (NH_4^+ by Et_3S^+ and Et_4P^+) as in 4 and anion replacement (SO_4^{2-} by BeF_4^{2-} and PO_3F^{2-}) as in 5-7. The latter work based on size, number of valence electrons and other structural considerations remains particularly noteworthy.

Keywords : Double sulfates, double double sulfates, isomorphism, solid solutions.

Introduction

During his long research career Rây got involved with the chemistry of double sulfates in a major way twice. First, during 1885-1887 for his independent doctoral work (D.Sc. degree) in Edinburgh University as a Gilchrist Scholar. The problem concerned in the D.Sc. work was to find out if two double sulfates could combine in stoichiometric proportions to yield a 'double-double' sulfate as a distinct entity. Second, during 1928-1930 as Palit Professor in College of Science. Here the problem tackled concerned the isomorphous replacement of sulfate ions by certain other anions. A little earlier (1927-1928) possible replacement of ammonium cation in double sulfates by some other complex cations was also examined. In this article we review Rây's findings on the above problems.

Before we proceed to that the background of the origin of Rây's interest in double sulfates will be briefly chronicled. In Edinburgh, chemistry class lectures during B.Sc. were delivered by the renowned organic chemist Alexander Crum Brown. But the practical class was looked after by capable demonstrators like John Gibson who had worked with Robert Bunsen at Heidelberg, Gibson's lessons and tips on laboratory activities and methods of analysis much benefited Rây. This got reflected when he searched for his doctoral research prob-

lem on experimental work involving synthesis and analysis of a new group of compounds with the hope of defining some unifying principle. From literature search he chose the then quite active area of double sulfate chemistry where he could also figure out an arena for his own work.

Except for long lists of compounds, inorganic chemistry was then in a poor state of understanding (compared to organic chemistry) with Mendeleev's periodic table as the only major development. But this disadvantage was also an opportunity for an ardent experimentalist like Rây. This was the beginning of Rây's long and distinguished career on various facets of inorganic chemistry which spanned over decades witnessing inorganic research traversing from an age of guessing and groping to one of enlightened structure-based accounting. We have already documented several of his contributions¹⁻⁵.

Doctoral Work

Double sulfates of type 1 have been known from at least 1850. Some of these occur in nature and they can be generally prepared by cocrystallizing constituent sulfates from aqueous media. At present the known list of salts include $Mm = \text{K, Rb, Cs, Tl, NH}_4$ and $Mb = \text{V, Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Mg, Cd}$. Not all of these were

knows in Rây's time. At that time nothing was known about the internal structure of **1** and chemists speculated that higher order sulfates may also occur. In 1855 Vohl reported⁶ that 1 : 1 composites of two double sulfates of type **1** can occur as **2** (double double sulfate incorporating Mb and Mb') as a distinct entity.

Mb = bivalent

Mm = monovalent

1

2

This was contradicted by Aston and Pickering (1886)⁷. There has been other claims and contradictions.

As his doctoral work Rây decided to reexamine the matter on double double sulfates. The sulfates of concern to him had Mm = K, NH₄ and Mb, Mb' = Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd, Mg. His preparative method consisted leaving a nearly saturated aqueous solution of a mixture of constituent sulfates taken in equivalent or nearly equivalent proportions to evaporate spontaneously. Crystallization proceeded well and after a time it more or less ceased. The crop was collected for chemical analysis. He found the data to fit well to the flexible double double sulfate composition **3** where x and y are small integers⁸.

3

The internal structure of double sulfates **1** started becoming clear only when X-ray diffraction studies were undertaken after 1930. Now the detailed structures of many of these salts are known^{9,10}. The entire family is monoclinic and belong to the same space group. Each Mb²⁺ ion is bonded to six water molecules in a nearly octahedral fashion. Hydrogen atoms of water molecule hydrogen bond with sulfate oxygen atoms forming a stable network. The Mm⁺ ions bind to the Mb-H₂O-SO₄ core either coordinatively (K⁺) or by the H-bonds (NH₄⁺). The different double sulfates are isostructural and nearly isometric and they form solid solutions (mixed crystals) freely. And it is now clear that all double double sulfates including those of Rây are only solid solutions (or mixtures thereof) of the constituent double salts. There is just no driving force for the formation of any new phase when double sulfates are mixed. A complete and critical ac-

count of the doctoral work can be found elsewhere¹¹.

Cation replacement in double sulfates

These experiments were reported by Rây and his students during 1927-1929. The idea was to replace the usual monovalent cation Mm⁺ in **1** by more complex species such as trialkyl sulfonium^{12,13}, R₃S⁺ and tetraethylphosphonium¹⁴, Et₄P⁺ ion. Accordingly the authors synthesized with some difficulty the sulfates (R₃S)₂SO₄ (R = Me, Et) and (Et₄P)₂SO₄ and cocrystallized each of them with sulfates of bivalent metals. In this manner they were able to isolate several series of double sulfates all of which¹²⁻¹⁴ will not be cited here. We cite the three types

Mb = Mn, Fe, Co, Ni, Ni, Cu, Zn, Cd, Mg

Mb = Fe, Co, Ni, Ni, Zn, Cd

Mb = Co, Ni, Mg

4

noted in **4**. In these the number of molecules of water of crystallization is either 8 or 10. In no case any double sulfate with 6H₂O as in **1** could be isolated. They did some experiments on thermal dehydration/decomposition of the salts.

Anion replacement in double sulfates

This work reported in 1929-1930 is well conceived and has the necessary structural basis^{15,16}. Salts of type **1** are essentially ionic solids. By the 1920's good progress was being made by chemists (like Lewis, Langmuir and others) and physicists in defining the principles that determine the structure of ionic crystals. It became clear that different complex ions having the same number of atoms should give rise to isomorphous salts provided their sizes are similar and they have the same number of valence electrons meaning that they have the same net charge. Many examples had been known in literature which could now be understood like the isomorphism of BF₄⁻, SO₃F⁻ and ClO₄⁻ salts or TiF₆²⁻, NbOF₅²⁻ and MoO₂F₄²⁻ salts.

In Rây's laboratory this principle was deftly employed by Dr. P. B. Sarkar and others in the case of the dianionic triad BeF₄²⁻, PO₃F²⁻ and SO₄²⁻ primarily with the objective of isolating isomorphous double salts. All the three

anions have five atoms and thirtytwo valence electrons. Goldschmidt ionic radii of Be^{2+} , P^{5+} and S^{6+} were nearly equal ($\sim 0.34 \text{ \AA}$) and the same was true for O^{2-} and F^- ($\sim 1.33 \text{ \AA}$) thus ensuring that the sizes of the anion triad were about the same. It was probably a bit too early for Rây to talk about their tetrahedral shape and he did not mention this in his papers^{15,16}. However the molecular volumes of the salts K_2BeF_4 , $\text{K}_2\text{PO}_3\text{F}$ and K_2SO_4 were found to be closely similar. The salts were isomorphous and formed mixed crystals i.e. solid solutions in all proportions.

This done, they proceeded to the main task of isolating type **1** salts with SO_4^{2-} replaced by $\text{PO}_3\text{F}^{2-}/\text{BeF}_4^{2-}$. For this they cocrystallized the relevant constituent salts from aqueous media and succeeded in isolating salts such as those in **5** in crystalline form. In going from **1** to **5** $(\text{Mm})_2\text{SO}_4$ has been replaced by $(\text{Mm})_2\text{BeF}_4$ or $(\text{Mm})_2\text{PO}_3\text{F}$ ($\text{Mm} = \text{K}, \text{NH}_4$) and Mb of MbSO_4 spanned the 3d series as well as Mg, Zn, Cd. All the salts were isomorphous with corresponding type **1** double sulfates. Also isomorphous were the salts of type **6** (prepared similarly to **5**) where sulfate in both MbSO_4 and Mm_2SO_4 have been replaced by $\text{PO}_3\text{F}^{2-}/\text{BeF}_4^{2-}$.

5

6

7

To complete these fascinating experiments on isomorphous anion replacement in **1**, they prepared alums incorporating $\text{PO}_3\text{F}^{2-}/\text{BeF}_4^{2-}$ as illustrated in **7** all isomorphous with common alum $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot \text{Mm}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Concluding remarks

Rây's long research career (1885-1930) spans over a period in which inorganic chemistry metamorphosed from a nearly empirical platform to one where actions started getting organized on structural principles – thanks to the progress made both in theory and experimental methods. This change in reflected in many of Rây's research endeavours. His involvement with double salts is a model example. His claim of isolation of type **3** double double sulfates in doctoral work was perfectly legitimate in those days when the only tool available to him was elemental analysis and nothing was known about the structure of double sulfates. When this became known decades later, one could see that the double double sulfates were only solid solutions and no new phase formation was involved. His terminal work on isomorphous replacement as in **5**, **6** and **7** was based on rational structural principles and stands unchanged.

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